

IMPORTANCE OF ASSESSMENT IN ELT

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Abstract

Both in the teaching and learning processes, assessment plays a vital role in education. Teachers can categorize and grade their students, provide feedback, and plan their lessons properly with the help of appropriate assessment. Because of the recent changes in assessment methods, scientists and educators have been more interested in the specifications of assessment procedures in the context of teaching foreign languages and the learning process. The assessment methods are regarded as the fundamentals of assessment in the teaching and learning of foreign languages. They have to do with authenticity, practicality, dependability, validity, and wash back. These previously mentioned concepts are primarily useful for identifying the impacts of assessment and reviewing any concerns that may arise in the classroom between the teacher and student.

Keywords: assessment, forms, evaluation, testing, feedback

The idea that students should participate actively in class is supported by learner-centric techniques, which are a novel approach to foreign language instruction. In a similar spirit, language instructors employ evaluation exercises in the classroom to determine the degree of pupil acquisition. One could argue that assessment is a process that takes time and entails gathering data and information about pupils' growth. In order to guide and enhance continuous learning, assessment is essential to the educational process and plays a big part (Cowie & Bell, 1999). As per Pierce (2002), as mentioned in Kırmızı & Kömeç (2016), evaluation plays a vital role in every educational endeavor involving teaching and learning .It guides daily instructional decisions, assists in identifying students' areas of strength and weakness in relation to classroom instruction, and gives them targeted feedback to enhance their learning. Additionally, assessment gives teachers quick feedback so they can modify their methods of instruction to fit the different learning styles of their pupils. Teachers should use several assessments to evaluate student achievement and assign grades. A vital instrument for measuring the learning process are tests, exams, and evaluation models. The primary components of teaching and

learning activities are assessment and evaluation. Their definitions are extremely similar, and they are frequently used interchangeably. They do, however, differ from one another in certain ways. The term "assessment" refers to a broad category of procedures and strategies used to collect data on student aptitude, comprehension, and motivation (Allan, 1999; Ekbatani & Pierson, 2000; Lambert & Lines, 2000). Gathering the data required to ascertain if a program achieves its objectives is the process of evaluation. It seeks to ascertain which approaches are effective and ineffective (Kaufman, Guerrero, Platt, 2006). These definitions make it clear that assessment is the process or action, and evaluation is the approach. This suggests that assessment techniques can be used during the evaluation process.

Selection of Assessment

A choice among the possibilities that are offered for assessment and the likelihood that these preferences will be realized are the definitions of assessment selection. It may be claimed that the sort of evaluation can either increase or decrease tension and anxiety, depending on the preferences of the teacher and students. Few studies (Black & William, 1998; K. H., Wang, T. H. Wang, W. L. Wang, & Huang, 2006; Watering, Gijbels, Dochy, & Rijt, 2008) specifically examine student preferences and assessment formats, as well as which students will perform better on favored formats. According to Berry (2010), assessments, tests, and evaluation procedures might bring back unpleasant emotions for students, including anxiety, a fear of failing, and concern for what other people might think of their skills. These unfavorable opinions could have a significant impact on performance. This circumstance might deter students from being motivated to pick up a language. Maximizing acquisition throughout the learning process can be achieved by the teacher's continuous assessment of the learner. It is essential to combine classic and current testing methods in order to effectively handle student fear or concerns about evaluation. The goal of traditional assessment methods is to evaluate a student's or learner most recent performance or activities using resources such as fill-in-the-blank tests, cloze exams, and test questions. Instead of focusing on long-term achievement, these performance-oriented testing activities might help learners succeed in the short term. For these reasons, it is imperative that teachers maintain the maximum level of motivation and that students have no tension or worry. In essence, the choice of assessment can have a big influence on how foreign languages are taught and learned. Scientists describe evaluation as the procedure of gathering information in order to pinpoint issues. There are

five main categories of decisions that assessments might lead to. These choices relate to student progress evaluation, instructional planning, screening, referral, and classification. Academic, behavioral, or physical issues may be the focus of assessment for each of these choices (Shapiro, 1987). Teachers of foreign languages typically use tests and exams to gather data on students' language proficiency.

Alternative Assessments

English language teachers are starting to realize that new alternative evaluation approaches need to be developed in order to properly track and assist the learning development of their pupils. These innovative assessment techniques, which are frequently used over a predefined period of time, concentrate on assessing students' capacity to use language in natural ways in everyday contexts. Furthermore, a growing number of authentic assessments, such as projects, performance assignments, concept maps, journals, posters, instructors, and student interviews, as well as portfolios, drama, theater, self- and peer-assessment, and portfolios, have been used in classrooms (Anıl & Acar, 2008; Büyüktokatlı & Bayraktar, 2014). The following are the ways that authentic and conventional testing differ from one another.

According to Richards and Renandya, (2002) "alternative assessment has been described as an alternative to standardized

testing and all of the problems found with such testing. There is no single definition of alternative assessment. assessment is different from traditional testing in that it actually asks students to show what they can do. Students are evaluated on what they integrate and produce rather than on what they are able to recall and reproduce. Thus, alternative assessment is realized in classroom activities and reflects and suits the requirements for the syllabus. Thanks to alternative assessment, learning becomes more authentic because it helps students improve their decision making and problem solving skills (Brualdi, 1996). Teachers are also able to gain insight about their course effectiveness and make alterations if necessary.

The principles of Assessment

Assessment includes information about student awareness, understanding, perception and attitude to learning. Assessment answers the needs of the student and is central to teacher planning, including testing. In this vein, Brown & Abeywickrama (2010) and Sariçoban (2011) argue that standardized tests have been most often associated with the terms of the following assessment

principles: authenticity, reliability, validity, and the washback effect. Here they are explained in detail.

a) is consistent in its conditions
b) gives clear directions for evaluation
c) has uniform rubrics for evaluating
d) contains assignments that are unambiguous for the test-taker, (Brown & Abeywickrama, 2010). Richards and Renandya (2002) say that if a procedure is valid, it is reliable and it gives the same conclusions. The possible realization rate is extremely high, for example if a student's written story shares the same, or at least highly similar, characteristics of his/her subsequent writing. The fourth primary principle of foreign language testing is washback effect. According to Brown (2004), and Anderson, Rourke, Archer, & Garrison (2001), this principle is defined as the effect of testing on teaching and learning a foreign language. Another point of view on the washback principle is that the washback effect may denote both the promotion and the self-consciousness of language learning. This principle reflects how tests influence both teaching and learning. The following issues have to be put into consideration when using washback;

a) positively influences what and how teachers teach and how students learn
b) suggests students have a chance to prepare
d) gives students feedback data to evaluate language achievement
e) provides conditions for peak performance by the student (Brown & Abeywickrama, 2011)

CONCLUSION

Teachers and students can learn about the amount of knowledge, abilities, challenges in learning a foreign language, and most effective activities and approaches by testing related evaluations. Testing is a tool for assessing student performance and can be applied to establish precise standards or a scale. Testing can be used with the objects to test, measure, and evaluate, but assessment has a larger meaning that involves considering and evaluating a person (Akpınar & Çakildere, 2013; Brown, 2004). The word assessment means the consideration of a person and an evaluation of them, and has a wider rationale than testing (Akpınar & Çakildere, 2013; Brown, 2004), which can be used with the items, to test, measure and evaluate. In the light of alternative assessments, teachers may identify what is important in their teaching process and select assessment strategies suitable for the characteristics of the learners. Knowing and organizing principles of assessment, develops the

planning of assessment of a foreign language. So the following issues have to be taken into consideration by the teacher, in the planning of teaching foreign languages with regard to assessment.

In conclusion, it is now well known how important assessment is to the language learning process. For kids to learn a language, assessment is crucial. It is essential to the learning process because it helps students apply what they already know to new information.

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